

The Extinction Coefficient of Br_3 -ions and its Function in Photochemical Reactions.

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It is a common fact that in the oxidation of many organic acids by bromine the velocity falls off rapidly with time. It is known that in such oxidation processes the negative ions of the acids are generally reactive. The rapid fall in the velocity is due to two factors. Firstly, hydrobromic acid which is one of the products of reaction throws back the dissociation of the reacting acid and secondly, the bromine ions of hydrobromic acid react with Br_2 -molecules with the production of Br_3 -ions which are quite inactive and hence the concentration of the effective bromine molecules is diminished.

If, in the beginning, sufficient HBr is added to maintain a fairly constant concentration of H^+ ions, and then varying amounts of potassium bromide are added, the reaction velocity is found to be proportional to the concentration of free bromine present at any instant, thus showing clearly that in dark reactions Br_3 -ions are not at all reactive.

Many such reactions are also accelerated by light. The object of the present investigation was to find out if the function of the Br_3 -ions is also the same in photochemical processes. Both bromine molecules and Br_3 -ions being coloured it is obvious that the incident radiations will be shared between the two. It is possible that the light absorbed by Br_3 -ions may in some way help the progress of the reaction or simply dissipate away.

Benrath (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1910, **74**, 115) has shown that in the oxidation of a tartaric acid by bromine in presence of an excess of HBr when the concentration of the acid is large in comparison to that of bromine, equal amounts of bromine are transformed in equal intervals. Even in absence of HBr , after some time when sufficient HBr accumulates in the system, the reaction becomes zero-molecular.

The same phenomenon has been observed in the oxidation of mandelic acid, lactic acid and some other organic acids by bromine in presence of a bromide. All these reactions follow the unimolecular

law in absence of any bromide. This behaviour must be obviously due to the influence of Br_3 -ions.

In order to find out the function of Br_3 -ions a knowledge of its extinction coefficient is essential. Since Br_3 -ions only exist in solutions in equilibrium with Br_2 -molecules, the method of determinations is obviously indirect.

The molecular extinction coefficient ϵ is given by the relation,

$$\epsilon = \frac{\log \tan \alpha_1 - \log \tan \alpha_2}{Cd}$$

where C and d are respectively the concentration of the substance and the depth of the absorption vessel, and α_1 and α_2 are the measure of the angles in positions 1 and 2 in a König-Marten spectrophotometer. From the known values of ϵ , C and d , the quantity $(\log \tan \alpha_1 - \log \tan \alpha_2)$ for any substance can be easily determined.

In the case of a solution containing Br_2 and KBr , the quantity $(\log \tan \alpha_{m1} - \log \tan \alpha_{m2})$ will be due to the absorption of light by Br_2 -molecules and Br_3 -ions. From the equilibrium relation $\text{Br}^- + \text{Br}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{Br}_3^-$ the concentration of free Br_2 and Br_3 -ions in any mixture can be easily calculated.

If C be the total Br_2 concentration and C_1 be the concentration of free bromine molecules,

$$\log \tan \alpha_1 - \log \tan \alpha_2 = \epsilon_{\text{Br}_3} \cdot C_1 d$$

$$\text{and } \epsilon_{\text{Br}_3} = \frac{(\log \tan \alpha_{m1} - \log \tan \alpha_{m2}) - \epsilon_{\text{Br}_2} \cdot Cd}{(C - C_1)d}$$

The quantities C , C_1 and d are known and ϵ_{Br_2} can be separately determined.

It is found that on the addition of a bromide to an aqueous solution of bromine, the red colour disappears and the solution becomes distinctly yellow. From this it can be inferred that Br_3 -ions will have very little absorption in the yellow and green regions, and large absorption in blue and violet light. Experimental results also corroborate this.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The determination of am_1 and am_2 was made by means of a König-Martens spectrophotometer which was calibrated by means of a quartz mercury lamp. The source of illumination was a 500 c.p. "point-o-lite" lamp. Aqueous solutions of pure bromine and of bromine containing KBr were introduced into absorption vessels of different depths and a number of readings were taken for each solution. The mean of them gave am_1 and am_2 . For the purpose of calculation of the concentrations of free Br_2 and Br_3 -ions in the mixture, the value of K was taken to be 0.065 as given by Jakowkin (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1896, 20, 19).

The following tables give the extinction coefficients of bromine molecules and Br_3 -ions.

TABLE I.

Blue light—436 μ .

Conc. of KBr.	Activity coeff.	Conc. of free bromine.	Conc. of Br_3 -ion.	Depth of the absorption vessel.	$\log \tan m_1$ — $\log \tan m_2$.	ϵ .
0	—	·003365	—	4 cm.	·785	58·2
0	—	·002048	—	,,	·5065	61·8
0	—	·00161	—	,,	·3855	59·9
						Mean 60 = ϵ_{Br_2}
·2	·75	·00167	·00328	2 cm.	·8188	97·6
·1	·8	·00101	·001225	4	·6975	[93]
·0667	·83	·001495	·001235	2	·4351	104·0
·05	·84	·000625	·000405	4	·3273	109·4
·0333	·87	·000941	·000414	2	·2095	117·0
·02272	·9	·00061	·000175	4	·2242	111·0
						Mean 108 = ϵ_{Br_3}

TABLE II.

Green light—546 $\mu\mu$.

Conc. of KBr.	Activity coeff.	Conc. of free bromine.	Conc. of Br ₃ -ions.	Depth of the absorption vessel.	$\log \tan m_1$ $-\log \tan m_2$	ϵ .
0	—	·04125	—	2 cm.	·361	4·4
0	—	·04125	—	4	·72	4·45
0	—	·01924	—	4	·327	4·08
						Mean 4·3 = ϵ_{Br_2}
·125	·79	·01147	·015	4 cm.	·248	·80
·0833	·81	·01682	·01388	4	·3313	·76
·0633	·81	·01682	·01388	2	·1661	·81
·0416	·85	·02592	·0101	2	·237	·70
						Mean ·76 = ϵ_{Br_3}

TABLE III.

Yellow light—579 $\mu\mu$.

0	—	·04125	—	2 cm.	·120	1·46
0	—	·04125	—	4	·2312	1·4
0	—	·01924	—	4	·1122	1·6
						Mean 1·5 = ϵ_{Br_2}
·2	·75	·00923	·01877	4 cm.	·0621	·09
·0416	·85	·02592	·0101	2	·0782	·02

Plotnikow (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1912, **79**, 357) gives the values of ϵ_{Br_2} as 59·5 for 436 $\mu\mu$, 4·52 for 546 $\mu\mu$ and 1·87 for 579 $\mu\mu$.

On account of very large absorption measurements in the violet region could not be followed with the spectrophotometer. This was, however, done with a quartz spectrotgraph, the source of illumination being a copper arc, which showed that for all the radiations beyond 435 $\mu\mu$, the extinction coefficient of Br₃-ions is much greater than that of Br₂.

The activity coefficients of KBr given in the above tables were taken from Lewis and Randall's "Thermodynamics."

It is seen from the results that Br₃-ions has practically no absorption in the yellow region while for green light it is much less than that

of Br_2 . In blue and violet light its absorption is very high. On account of exceedingly small absorption, the measurements for the yellow region were erratic.

It has been already stated that the value of the constant K for the equilibrium $\text{Br}^- + \text{Br}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{Br}_3^-$ has been taken to be 0.065. In a recent paper Hammick and others (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 2715) have shown that K has probably a higher value. Jakowkin's value 0.065 is for solution in which the concentration of bromine was in no case less than 0.04M and the electrolytes were assumed to be completely dissociated. His constants also show a tendency of regular increase with increasing dilution. In the reaction between formic acid and bromine by plotting the reciprocals of the monomolecular velocity constants against the Br-concentration Hammick and others (*loc. cit.*) obtained 0.07 as the value of K . The concentration of bromine in this case varied between 0.01M and 0.005M. The generally accepted value 0.065 is not far different from this. It is evident that if K has a higher value, the extinction coefficient of Br_3^- ions for blue or violet light will be correspondingly higher. In these experiments in blue light the total concentration of Br_2 lies between 0.001M and 0.005M, and in green and yellow light between 0.021M and 0.035M. Assuming that K does change with dilution, in each region it may be regarded as fairly constant. It can be seen that if we choose 0.1, a much higher value for K for blue light with 0.2M-KBr and 0.00485M- Br_2 , ϵ_{Br_3} changes from 97.6 to 103, and in the case of 0.05M-KBr and 0.00103M- Br_2 , the change is from 109.4 to 124. So the relative variation is not much. The concentration of tribromide ion is always very low: so its activity may be regarded as equal to its concentration. The values of ϵ_{Br_3} given in the foregoing tables are not very concordant but, considering the method of determination involved and the uncertainty about the value of K , they may be regarded as fairly constant.

The Function of Br_3^- ions in Photochemical Reactions.

For this purpose some reactions were studied which have no appreciable velocity in darkness. The solution of the reacting substances together with an aqueous solution of bromine containing different amounts of KBr was introduced into a reaction cell placed inside a double jacketed metal box and the temperature was kept constant by circulating water through the box by means of a pump.

The source of illumination was a "point-o-lite" lamp from which a parallel beam was obtained by means of a lens. The oxidation of mandelic acid and lactic acid was found to be quite suitable reactions because the dark reaction is negligible in comparison with the light reaction. The experimental results are given in the following tables. 2 C.c. of the reaction mixture were always titrated at regular intervals with a standard thiosulphate solution.

TABLE IV.

Mandelic acid—0.385*M*. Temperature—32°.KBr—0.2308*M*. Bromine—0.00669*M*.

No light filter was used.

Time in mins. ...	0	15	30	46	60
(<i>a-x</i>) ...	5.6	4.65	3.7	2.75	1.85
<i>x/t</i> ...	—	.0633	.0633	.0625	[.0607]

TABLE V.

Potassium bromide—0.462*M*.

Time in mins. ...	0	20	40	60	80
(<i>a-x</i>) ...	5.65	4.8	3.95	3.15	2.35
<i>x/t</i> ...	—	.0425	.0425	.040	.040

TABLE VI.

Mandelic acid—0.3846*M*.

Conc. of KBr.	Activity coeff.	Conc. of free Br ₂ .	Conc. of Br ₂ .	Free Br ₂ /Br ₂ .	<i>x/t</i> .
(1) .1154	.79	.00285 <i>M</i>	.003835 <i>M</i>	.74	.114
(2) .2308	.745	.00188 <i>M</i>	.00485	.39	.0625
(3) .2308	.745	.00223 <i>M</i>	.00821	.4	.065
(4) .4616	.7	.00114 <i>M</i>	.00555	.2	.041
(5) .4616	.7	.00226 <i>M</i>	.00918	.25	.049
(6) .23HBr		Total Br ₂ .0114 <i>M</i>	—	—	.0575

TABLE VII.

Potassium bromide—0.4615*M*. Bromine—0.00669 *M*.

Conc. of mandelic acid.	x/t .	Ratio of conc. of the acid.	Ratio of velocity constant.
.2308	.029	From (1) and (2)—1.67	1.45
.3846	.042	„ (2) and (3)—1.4	1.4
.5985	.059	„ (1) and (3)—2.33	2.03

It is evident from the results given in Table VI that as the ratio, free Br_2/Br_3 , increases the velocity constant increases irrespective of the total amount of bromine present initially. It is also quite apparent that the rate of the reaction is not at all governed by the amount of free bromine present but it is in some way determined by the ratio, free Br_2/Br_3 . Thus in experiments (4) and (5), the amount of free bromine varies as 1:2 but the velocity constants differ slightly because the ratios, free Br_2/Br_3 , differ slightly. This is also evident from a comparison of the other results as well. Hydrobromic acid gives a slightly lower value because the dissociation of the reacting acid is diminished. Table VII shows that the velocity constants are nearly proportional to the concentration of mandelic acid.

The temperature coefficient of the reaction was found to be 1.7-1.8 which is given in the following table.

TABLE VIII.

Mandelic acid—0.3846*M*. Bromine—0.0114 *M*.

Temperature.	Conc. of bromide.	x/t .	Temp. coeff.
32°	.3846 KBr	.05	} 1.68
42°	.3846 „	.084	
32°	.23 HBr	.059	} 1.8
42°	.23 „	.108	

Mandelic acid—0.231*M*. Bromine—0.00669*M*.

32°	.4616 KBr	.029	} 1.7
42°	.4616 „	.05	

In order to test if the free bromine molecules are alone responsible for the reaction, some measurements were carried out in blue light for which the extinction coefficients of bromine molecules and Br_3^- ions are known. The light filters used were the same as recommended by Plotnikow. The results of measurements are given in the following tables.

TABLE IX.

Blue light.

Mandelic acid—0.25M. Potassium bromide—0.15M. Bromine—0.0148M. Temperature—29.5°.

Time in minutes.	...	0	25	60	100	140
($a-x$)	...	7.4	6.7	5.75	4.65	3.55
x/t	...	—	.028	.027	.0275	.0275

TABLE X.

Potassium bromide—0.1M. Bromine—0.0104M.

Time in minutes.	...	0	25	50	75	100
($a-x$)	...	5.05	4.25	3.45	2.7	1.95
x/t	...	—	.032	.032	.030	.030

TABLE XI.

Lactic acid—0.54M.

Potassium bromide—0.167M. Bromine—0.0267M.

Time in minutes.	...	0	25	50	85	115
($a-x$)	...	13.35	12.2	11.1	9.5	8.2
x/t	...	—	.046	.044	.045	.043

TABLE XII.

Potassium bromide—0.1M. Bromine—0.0154M.

Time in minutes	...	0	15	40	60	90
($a-x$)	...	7.7	6.9	5.55	4.45	2.95
x/t	...	—	.053	.054	.055	.050

A summary of the results is given in Tables XII and XIII.

TABLE XIII.

Blue light.

Mandelic acid—0.25M. Temp.—29.5°.

Conc. of KBr.	Conc. of Br_2 .	Conc. of free Br_2 .	Conc. of Br_3^- .	x/t .	Energy absorbed in Hefners.	ψ^* .	$\frac{x/t}{\sqrt{\psi l}}$.	
A	.05	.042	.005395	.03255	.043	1.08	.56	.0565
B	.0833	.068	.00808	.00752	.037	1.15	.453	.051
C	.117	.0928	.00955	.01185	.0325	1.2	.37	.0487
D	.15	.116	.0056	.0092	.0256	1.16	.319	[.042]
E	.1	.08	.00485	.00556	.029	1	.4	.046
F	.0833	.069	.00803	.00752	.0183	.273	.453	.052
G	.05	.042	.005395	.003255	.0205	.25	.56	.055
H	.05	.042	.005395	.003255	.0122	.105	.56	.050

$$* \psi = \frac{\text{Free bromine}}{\text{Free bromine} + \text{Br}_2} \times \frac{\text{Br}_2}{\epsilon \text{Br}_2}$$

TABLE XIV.

Lactic acid—0.54M.

Conc. of KBr.	Conc. of Br_2 .	Conc. of free Br_2 .	Conc. of free Br_2 .	x/t .	Energy absorbed in Hefners.	ψ .	$\frac{x/t}{\sqrt{\psi l}}$.	
I	.167	.128	.00985	.01685	.045	1.26	.31	.072
J	.1	.08	.0073	.0081	.054	1.14	.41	.079
K	.167	.128	.0093	.0163	.0245	.3	.305	.080
L	.1	.08	.0070	.0078	.029	.275	.408	.0865
M	.1	.08	.0070	.0078	.019	.127	.408	.083

The significance of the quantity $x/t/\sqrt{\psi l}$ will be explained later. It will be shown that this quantity should be a constant. The results given in the foregoing tables, however, show that there is a fairly large variation. For the calculation of $x/t/\sqrt{\psi l}$ the following measurements and assumptions had to be made,

(1) The value of k for the equilibrium $\text{Br}^- + \text{Br}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{Br}_3^-$ was taken to be 0.065 for all the concentrations.

(2) ϵ_{Br_2} and ϵ_{Br_3} were determined separately and for the ratio $\epsilon_{\text{Br}_2}/\epsilon_{\text{Br}_3}$ a mean value of 1.3 was taken for the mean radiation $470\mu\mu$ transmitted by the Plotnikow filters, after experimentally testing the ratio for a few rays.

(3) The amount of energy absorbed by the different solutions was determined separately.

As some error is always involved in such measurements, the values of $x/t/\sqrt{\psi I}$ may be regarded as fairly constant.

The results also make certain facts obvious. It will be seen from experiments A, B and C that the amount of total bromine as well as the amount of free bromine and also the energy absorbed is much greater in C than in B or A; but x/t has a larger value in A than in B or C. It is clear therefore that neither the amount of total bromine nor the amount of free bromine is the determining factor. It will be also seen that the ratios, free Br_2/Br_3 are approximately as 1.7, 1 and 0.8 in A, B and C respectively. That is the zero-molecular constant increases as the ratio, free Br_2/Br_3 increases.

The dark reaction in the case of bromine and lactic acid in presence of KBr is exceedingly small. In the case of mandelic acid, however, it is quite appreciable. 0.25M-mandelic acid, 0.05M-KBr and 0.009M- Br_2 gave a zero-molecular constant, 0.0035 at 29.5° . The dark reaction is, of course, unimolecular but for the convenience of calculation, it has been regarded here as zero-molecular; the error due to this is quite negligible. In all cases the dark reaction has been deducted from the values of x/t .

Oxidation of tartaric acid (Ghosh and Mukherjee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2, 165) and of mandelic acid, β -phenyl lactic acid and similar other hydroxy acids by bromine in absence of any bromide shows that these reactions have got a temperature coefficient between 1.7 and 1.8. The velocity constants vary as the square root of intensity and are very nearly proportional to the concentration of the reacting acids. A review of the results given in the foregoing tables will show that the same facts are observed in presence of a bromide. Consequently the mechanism of the reactions must be regarded to be the same in presence or in absence of any bromide. The kinetics of the reactions stated above have been studied both in light and in darkness in absence of any bromide and

will be shortly published. These reactions, however, show some peculiar phenomena, namely the existence of a well defined induction period and a considerable increase in the velocity with diminution in the concentration of bromine. These peculiarities disappear completely in presence of sufficient potassium bromide (Benrath, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1910, **74**, 115; Purakayastha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, **5**, 721).

Discussion.

The experimental results recorded above bring out the following characteristics of the above photochemical reaction.

(1) That the reaction is zero-molecular in presence of excess of potassium bromide and the reacting organic acid.

(2) That the zero-molecular velocity constants increase as the ratio of free Br_2 : Br_3^- increases.

(3) That the velocity constant is proportional to the concentration of organic acid present in excess.

(4) That other experimental conditions remaining the same velocity constant is proportional to the square root of the intensity of incident blue light.

It appears that these observations can be quantitatively explained on the following hypothesis.

(i) Blue light absorbed by Br_3^- ions is simply dissipated away as waste thermal energy and does not contribute in the least to the progress of the photo-bromination.

(ii) Blue light absorbed by free bromine molecules brings about a state of equilibrium as given below :

the concentration of active bromine atoms being proportional to the square root of intensity of light absorbed by free bromine molecules alone.

If ϵ_1 be the molecular extinction coefficient of free bromine, and ϵ_2 the molecular extinction coefficient of Br_3^- ions and if I be the intensity of incident blue light which is completely absorbed by the reacting solution or which remains constant during the progress of the reaction, it follows at once that the fraction of light absorbed by free bromine molecules is

$$\psi = \frac{\epsilon_1 [\text{Br}_2]}{\epsilon_1 [\text{Br}_2] + \epsilon_2 [\text{Br}_3^-]}$$

or the intensity of light absorbed by free bromine molecules

$$\psi I = I \left[\frac{\epsilon_1 [\text{Br}_2]}{\epsilon_1 [\text{Br}_2] + \epsilon_2 [\text{Br}_3^-]} \right]$$

It is apparent that in presence of excess of potassium bromide, the ratio $\text{Br}_2/\text{Br}_3 = K[\text{Br}] = \text{Const.}$

$$\text{or } \frac{\epsilon_1 [\text{Br}_2]}{\epsilon_2 [\text{Br}_2]} = \text{Constant, or } \frac{\epsilon_1 [\text{Br}_2] + \epsilon_2 [\text{Br}_3]}{\epsilon_2 [\text{Br}_3]} = \text{Constant,}$$

$$\text{or } \psi = \text{Constant.}$$

That is, though during the progress of reaction, the absolute concentration of free bromine is continuously diminishing, the amount of light ψI absorbed by free bromine molecules alone remains the same throughout. Hence the concentration of active bromine atoms throughout the progress of photobromination $= K_1 \sqrt{\psi I}$, and the velocity of reaction,

$$dx/dt = K_2 \cdot K_1 \sqrt{\psi I} \cdot C \quad \dots (1)$$

where C is the concentration of reacting organic acid and K_2 the number of organic acid molecules reacted upon in a chain per each active atom of bromine produced. Since all the terms in the right hand side of the equation (1) are practically constant, $dx/dt = \text{constant}$. Hence the reaction is zero-molecular ;

$$\text{or } x/t = K \sqrt{\psi I}, \text{ or } \frac{x/t}{\sqrt{\psi I}} = K.$$

In Tables XIII and XIV, the values of I , ψ and $x/t/\sqrt{\psi I}$ are given in columns 7, 8 and 9 respectively. It will be noticed that the values of $x/t/\sqrt{\psi I}$ are fairly constant.

The increase in the values of x/t with the increase in the ratio free Br_2/Br_3 also makes it abundantly clear that the fraction of light absorbed by Br_2 -molecules is alone photochemically active. We have, therefore, clear evidence of the fact that blue light absorbed by Br_3 -ions becomes photochemically inert.

It should be mentioned here that the blue light obtained by using Plotnikow filters is not purely monochromatic. The filters also transmit a small amount of green and some other radiations. very

weekly absorbed by Br_2 and Br_3 . It has been noticed that the blue light appears distinctly yellowish green after transmission through a Br_2 and KBr solution. We have also observed that when the concentration of KBr is small and the intensity of blue light is fairly high (as in expt. A, Table XIII), x/t slightly falls off with time but where the intensity is low or the concentrations of Br_2 and KBr are fairly high, there is absolutely no fall in the values of x/t . The intensity measurements given in column 7 (Tables XIII and XIV) also show that though the concentrations of Br_2 and KBr vary widely, there is only a 12-13% change in the amount of energy absorbed by the different mixtures, which is no doubt mostly due to the green rays. This does not, however, mean that the amount of blue light does not remain constant during the progress of the reaction. This point has been thoroughly discussed by Ghosh and Purakayastha (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, **4**, 420). It has been shown that for blue light the variation in the amount of energy absorbed during the progress of the reaction when the final bromine concentration drops to a quarter of its initial value is negligible.

I am also of opinion that oxidation processes by iodine in presence of KI in light follow the same course. Some work in this direction is in progress.

Summary.

(1) The extinction coefficient of Br_3 -ion has been determined for $536\mu\mu$, $546\mu\mu$ and $579\mu\mu$.

(2) The oxidation of lactic and mandelic acids by bromine, which follows the unimolecular law, becomes zero-molecular in presence of a bromide in light.

(3) The zero-molecular constant increases with the free Br_2/Br_3 .

(4) The experimental results have been satisfactorily explained on the assumption that only the fraction of light absorbed by bromine molecules is photochemically active, and the energy absorbed by Br_3 -ions is photochemically inert.

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